

Aspiring for Social and Mental Empowerment of Women as Found in Literature

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Abstract

Theoretical interpretation and its implications of women empowerment have been widely discussed and written. Literature on women empowerment does not touch the roots of it. What we need to empower women today is changing the mental and social aspects. It is this mental conceptions and social views that determine the kind of empowerment today. If women are empowered socially and mentally they will withstand any kind of pressure from the society. This article talks about how mental and social empowerment of women can transform their lives in the society.

Keywords: Women Empowerment, Mental and social empowerment, literature

I feel it inevitable to discuss the term women empowerment in the present scenario as it has been wrongly understood by common people. The reason is that the meaning of this phrase has been altered due to various reasons. Though the issues of girl child education, child marriage and other women related social issues have been uprooted from the society to a considerable degree, their social and mental empowerment is still bleak. Women are strong enough economically compared to their previous generation but do they gain respect and honour that they deserve? Do they experience mental freedom in spite of their financial position?

People many a time associate gender and sex as synonyms. What they fail to understand is gender is not sex. Sex is based on the biology of man and woman. Gender denotes the nature of works, responsibilities, expectations, liabilities and social tradition expected from a particular sex. Thus gender discrimination is not from nature though sex is natural. This is well-asserted by Maitrai Pushpa, a journalist and social reformer, "God did not create male-female at the time of shaping universe. Human, for their facility distributed the works. They divided rights and duties also with the passage of time. But suddenly women awake and started knowing the closed door. Though those doors are still closed but with their efforts they made a small aperture for fresh air" (Khel Tamasha, 2011). Thus literature plays an enormous role in bringing mental and social empowerment of women.

Let us discuss how Indian literature helped women in attaining social and mental empowerment. Different genres in Indian English literature, have given women the important place. The aim behind depicting women was to empower the position of women, particularly women in India. The first Indian woman poet who wrote in English was Toru Dutt. Through Sita and Savitri, she displayed the archetypes of Indian womanhood, their suffering, reinforcement of conventional myths and self-sacrificing roles in a patriotic manner. Another famous poet, Kamla Das who wrote an emotional and strong feminine confessional poetry. Through her poems she explored the man-woman relationship as a major theme. Her poems were fashioned on woman's suppression by the men in the society, through the string of relationship. *Life of Single Women*, was portrayed in such a manner that brought out a sympathetic attitude in the reader, and thus generated pathos in her poems.

The Diasporas, Like Jhumpa Lahiri and Bharati Mukherje ventured into bringing the problem of female suppression, exploitation and gave a new place and identity to the modern women. In their novel, the prominent theme was self-discovery and multiculturalism. Anita Desai, in her novels psychological novels, painted the image of a suffering woman immersed with her inner world, her sulking frustration and the storm within. Through such characters, she differentiates between male-centred and female - centred narrative. In her novel, she explored the diasporic sensibility that dealt with the fortune of immigrants. The concept of home and migration is very much embedded in Bharati Mukherjee *Desirable Daughters*. It is the sense of migration which brings about a change to the identity of Padma, who has finally made New York her home, her land of choice. But her absolute attachment to her home makes her the preserver and sustainer of Bengali custom in America. The foreign culture thus fails to disrupt her traditional identity.

Besides Indian feminist writers who dedicated themselves for women empowerment, I would like to discuss also the commendable contribution of Henrik Ibsen, George Bernard Shaw and Margaret Atwood for their scintillating contribution to social and mental empowerment of women.

Ibsen's *Doll House* was published in the year 1879. It was the first novel that became the pioneer to advocate the independency of women. Ibsen's plot in the play revolved around the financial empowerment of women. The protagonist Nora Helmer lived peacefully, joyfully and happily in her doll house. She was free and independent. But it was snatched from her by her husband because of a forgery she committed seven years back to save her husband. Through Nora Ibsen brought the importance of independence for women. As she was not earning she depended totally on her husband. She committed forgery for her husband but when she needed his support, he abandoned her. This is beautifully expressed in her words as,

"Yes... While I was at home with father he used to tell me all his opinions, and I held the same opinions. If I had others I said nothing about them, because he wouldn't have liked it. He used to call me his doll-child, and played with me as I played with my dolls. Then I came to live in your house-..."

I mean I passed from father's hand into yours. You arranged everything according to your taste, and I got the same taste as you or I pretended to Here I have been your doll wife, just as at home I used to be papa's doll's child (*A Doll's House*, p. 178)."

Expressing her disappointment, she left the house in search of her identity. This reminds every woman in the society that it is essential to be independent in the society as they need to be mentally and socially empowered.

George Bernard Shaw is another important personality who projected women empowerment through his characters. The character of Louka in "*Arms and the Man*" is the classical example of women's equality and power.

Louka, a maid servant in the house of major Petkoff, is a very shrewd woman. She finds Major Sergius Saranoff, would be son in law of major Petkoff. She with her shrewdness win the love of Sergius, to fulfil her ambition to be a rich women as her mistress, Katherine and Raina, wife and daughter of major Petkoff respectively. She very cleverly changes the mind of Sergius from Raina to herself. Her shrewdness may be experienced with her dialogue to Sergius in which she said-

“I would marry the man I loved, which no other queen in Europe has the courage to do. If I loved you, though you would be as far beneath me as I am beneath you, I would dare to be the equal of my inferior. Would you dare as much if you loved me? No: if you felt the beginning of love for me, you would not let it grow. You would not dare: you would marry a rich man’s daughter because you would be afraid of what other people would say of you (Arms and the Man, p. 146).”

Shaw portrays that women can be bold and courageous in all their situations. It is clearly seen when Louka scolds Nicola, a male servant and to whom she was betrothed. She said, “I believe you would rather be my servant than my husband; you would make more out of me. Oh! I know that soul of yours....Go and put those logs on the fire: that’s the sort of thing you understand (Arms and the Man, p. 138).”

The dialogue above shows the path of the women in male dominating society that they are not mere lifeless objects but they have their own identity which they deserve in the society. They are not born as second fiddle to the men but as complimentary beings. Thus the role of literature in the empowerment of women is vital.

It is an undeniable fact that mere economic betterment alone is not enough for the empowerment of women. Women empowerment has to be placed on social and mental sphere so that women deserve what they need.

In India, Women Empowerment was a thought-provoking task and one needs to admit that gender discrimination was prevalent for many years. This social malice cannot be removed without strict laws and their implementation, as these policies should be implemented in actual terms. The growth of women was stunted in the society as the powerful forces of the society never tried to uplift the position of women at different levels. In India, women are marginalized at every level of the society whether in social, economic, political participation and gender disparity also exists.

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